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Interdisciplinary Training Webinar (release 1) D3.5

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the *Cryomicroscopy for macromolecular structure determination* webinar - the first in the planned series of 9 Interdisciplinary Training Webinars for the Q-SORT project.

The Interdisciplinary Training Webinars are part of Work Package 3 **Theory, optical testing, and TEM implementation of generalised Sorter** [Months: 1-41], Task 3.5 - Interdisciplinary Training Webinars (M6, M11, M12, M18, M24, M26, M30, M36, M41).

The present document is comprised of 4 Chapters, including Introduction and Conclusions.

The Introduction describes what a webinar is.

Chapter 2 summarises what we mean by Interdisciplinary Training Webinars and what their function is within Q-SORT.

Chapter 3 illustrates context, aims, and content of the first Interdisciplinary Training Webinar of Q-SORT.

The conclusions outline future plans for the Interdisciplinary Training Webinars.

1 INTRODUCTION - WHAT IS A WEBINAR?

A webinar is a web-based seminar which can be streamed either live or on demand. It might be just a simple audio stream, or it might include visual aids, such as PowerPoint slides, recorded video clips, or live software demonstrations.

The experience of a webinar attempts to reproduce the benefits of attending a seminar. Audience members can ask questions and the speaker can survey or poll the audience and get feedback as he or she delivers the information.

Webinar technology providers need to support these interactive elements in addition to the basic delivery of the audio and video streams. Keyboard chat features and Q&A are usually subject to more control, whereby the presenters can see messages from the audience and choose whether to broadcast them to all participants, ignore them, or reply privately.

The Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Webinars make use of Vimeo as a platform for playback and of Facebook Live as a platform for live streaming. We chose these platforms as they provide the best value for money and offer the added advantage of being very widespread. On both platforms, users are able to pose questions by posting comments below the video. Answers can be provided by specialists during or after the webinar.

2 THE Q-SORT INTERDISCIPLINARY TRAINING WEBINARS

The Q-SORT project is intrinsically interdisciplinary, being born from the cross-fertilisation of three subjects: light optics (UG, MPI), electron microscopy (CNR, FZJ, UMR, FEI), and biology (MU).

The silo-breaking nature of Q-SORT provides added value through the following cross-fertilisation dynamics: microscopists borrow techniques from light optics specialists and explain back the challenges of the new measurements; biologists explain to physicists the problems that usually arise when studying proteins and suggest alternative proteins for investigation; physicists develop the quantum mechanical approach for cryo-TEM; biologists communicate a priori knowledge to light optics theoreticians in order to streamline efforts in the project work-packages (WP3-WP5).

In order to facilitate mutual learning between physicists and biologists, as well as to foster possible further applications to biology and the life sciences, 9 Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinars have been planned during the lifetime of the project. Their main aim is to function as aids to facilitate the highly interdisciplinary work in WP3 and in the other research WPs. They will do so by providing opportunities for training and mutual learning mentored by senior scientists, for forging a common language, for exchanging ideas for further joint research.

However important their role within Q-SORT, these seminars are meant for everyone, hence the choice to propose them as webinars, so as to reach as wide an audience as possible.

The Interdisciplinary Training Webinars introduce a sort of 'intermediate level' in the communication of science: i.e. their nature is intermediate between the specialist-to-specialist character of discipline-specific colloquia, talks, and articles and the broad appeal of conventional public understanding of science.

This is why, besides their facilitating function within WP3 and the other research WPs, the Interdisciplinary Training Webinars also play an important role in the dissemination and engagement process. Together with the Website, they ensure that Q-SORT will reach a broad range of pertinent audiences across Europe and beyond.

In the following paragraph we describe the first of the 9 Interdisciplinary Training Webinars planned for Q-SORT.

3 THE Q-SORT FIRST INTERDISCIPLINARY TRAINING WEBINAR:

CRYOMICROSCOPY FOR MACROMOLECULAR STRUCTURE DETERMINATION

The *Cryomicroscopy for macromolecular structure determination* Interdisciplinary Training Webinar was recorded during the second day of the Q-SORT Kick-off Meeting, which was held in Modena on October 02-03, 2017 with the support of CNR NANO (<http://www.nano.cnr.it/index.php?mod=men&id=292>).

This first webinar, which took place before any social media platform was activated, was webcast live via Skype to interested parties - namely the members of the Q-SORT consortium who weren't able to join the seminar in person. The webinar was recorded with two cameras, then edited and mastered for successive on-demand viewing.

The content of the Webinar was agreed upon by the Project Coordinator, Dr. Vincenzo Grillo (CNR) with Prof. Peter Peters (University of Maastricht) and Dr. Luca Marco Carlo Giberti (QED).

Being at the very beginning of the Project, this first webinar was conceived mainly in order to introduce the other Q-SORT partners (mostly physicists) to the applications of cryomicroscopy to the study of biological systems. It has thus been tailor made to be watched on demand: interested parties can re-play it at their convenience by clicking on the following password-protected links:

on the Q-SORT Website:

<http://www.qsort.eu/webinar1-cryomicroscopy-for-structure-determination/>

on Vimeo:

<https://vimeo.com/262658776>

The password for both versions is:

Q-SORT_Webinar1

This was the first in a series of interdisciplinary workshops/webinars aimed at promoting dialogue between the physics and biology/biochemistry communities. These provide an opportunity for mutual learning and fruitful 'cross pollination' between groups.

3.1 TECHNICAL DESCRIPTION

The webinar covers the following topics:

- cryomicroscopy sample preparation
- cryomicroscopy imaging
- dose problems

It aims to prime the transfer of knowledge from biochemists specialised in cryomicroscopy to the physicists community at large.

The aim of the webinar is to provide to other scientists an introduction to the applications of cryomicroscopy to the study of biological systems, highlighting systems of interest and problems that might be addressed by improving physical techniques. Users are able to pose questions by commenting in the Comments section of the video. User questions will be answered by cryomicroscopy specialists.

The experience in Modena was successful and followed by a very active Q&A.

Figure 1 - Screenshot from Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinar no. 1

Figure 2 - Screenshot from Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinar no. 1

3.2 THE FIRST INTERDISCIPLINARY TRAINING WEBINAR ON THE Q-SORT WEBSITE

In the *Result of the Review of your H2020 project 766970 — Q-SORT* the following observation was made:

The deliverable D3.5 “Interdisciplinary Training Webinar (release 1)” needs revision as the webinar was inaccessible to reviewers due to a wrong password.

The deliverables “D3.6 and D3.7 “Interdisciplinary Training Webinar (release 2 and 3)” need also revision. The goal of these webinars was to inform physicists and biochemists of the new possibilities afforded by outstanding technologies. Hence the benefit of such a webinar for the members of Q-SORT is enormous. Nevertheless, it would be useful for wider audience, if the resumé of the presentation will be made; such a comprehensible text will offer a better understanding of the topics. In order to comply to this request a dedicated webpage for each webinar has been created on the Q-SORT website featuring:

1. the webinar;
2. a short description of the webinar thought for the general public;
3. a short bio of the speaker who gave the talk.

The link to the webpage is:

<http://www.qsort.eu/webinar1-cryomicroscopy-for-structure-determination/>

The password is:

Q-SORT_Webinar1

An overview and a screenshot of the webpage are provided below.

Cryomicroscopy for macromolecular structure determination / Raimond Ravelli, University of Maastricht (The Netherlands)

The first Interdisciplinary Training Webinar covers the following topics:

- dose problem in electron microscopy
- cryomicroscopy sample preparation
- protein structure determination in microbiology
- cryomicroscopy imaging
- computer-assisted structural reconstruction
- phase plate use in cryomicroscopy.

The webinar provides other scientists with an introduction to the techniques and applications of cryomicroscopy to the study of biological systems. Cryomicroscopy is done in a specially modified transmission electron microscope, which allows the quick transfer of specially frozen samples into the microscope column, and their subsequent imaging.

The talk explains the use of Volta phase plates, which allow one to convert the phase variation that the sample imparts to the electron beam into an amplitude variation, which is directly observable as an image. The webinar also illustrates the equipment and techniques that are used in order to prepare and then flash-freeze the liquid solution containing the molecules that are to be studied in the cryo electron microscope. It is important that the solution ends up as vitrified ice, as the amorphous structure of such glass-like ice greatly aids the imaging of the molecules.

The talk also highlights molecules and systems of interest, as well as problems that could be addressed by improving physical techniques.

The chief aim of this webinar is to function as primer on cryoTEM. It also aims to initiate the transfer of knowledge from biochemists specialised in cryomicroscopy to the physicists community of Q-SORT, as well as to the physics community at large.

About the speaker

Raimond Ravelli is a structural biologist specialised in X-ray crystallography and electron microscopy. After his study (chemistry, cum laude, 1992) and PhD (1998), he moved to the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (Grenoble outstation) where he became team leader as well as principal beamline scientist on world's first third-generation multiple wavelength anomalous dispersion beamline ID14-4 at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility. Catalysed by a NWO personal career grant (Vidi, 2007), he moved back to the Netherlands as assistant professor in electron microscopy. In 2014, he started at the Maastricht University to help set up the new Institute of Nanoscopy. He employs physics, chemistry, engineering and informatics to study biological structures at the highest possible resolution and develops new methods for structure determination. He determined a wide variety of macromolecular structures and complexes, including proteins involved in neurotransmission, cytoskeletal components, viral infection, and protein secretion. He developed both hard- and software to streamline the process of automated data collection and processing on both X-ray crystallography beamlines as well as the electron microscope. His large-scale electron microscopic images have been displayed at the museum Boijmans van Beuningen in Rotterdam (temporary exhibition Science and Art) and Naturalis Biodiversity Museum in Leiden (permanent exhibition), and have been included in the Guinness World Records book as largest digital recording (2013). He (co-)authored almost 100 peer-reviewed scientific papers (cited ~7100 times, H index of 43). He is scientific referee of numerous journals, member of numerous national and international advisory committees, chairman of the Dutch crystallography association, and (co-)organizer of numerous national and international meetings and workshops.

Screenshot of the third interdisciplinary training webinar page on the Q-SORT website

4 CONCLUSIONS

This is the first Interdisciplinary Training Webinar produced by Q-SORT.

In the past few years we have seen a consistent rise in the popularity and value of webinars as an essential training, communication, and engagement tool.

The video of the webinar also offers a unique opportunity for engagement. The project will continue to promote on-demand webinars so that their audiences will get larger and more engaged, and spend more time watching webinars, both live and on-demand. In planning the next webinars we will evaluate the effectiveness of this first one and use it as a guideline to help the Q-SORT consortium creating, promoting, and delivering even more successful webinars.

ANNEX 1: CRYOMICROSCOPY FOR MACROMOLECULAR STRUCTURE DETERMINATION

Cryo-EM

For macromolecular structure determination

Raimond Ravelli
M4i, Maastricht University

QSORT – Kickoff Meeting
October 2-3, 2017 - Modena, Italy

Outline

- Resolution Revolution
- Single Particle Analysis
- Phase Plate
- Sample Preparation

Bonus

- *In situ* structural biology

QSORT – Kickoff Meeting
October 2-3, 2017 - Modena, Italy

“The Revolution will not be crystallised”

Nature, 10 sep 2015, Ewen Callaway

“MOVE OVER X-RAY CRYSTALLOGRAPHY. CRYO-ELECTRON MICROSCOPY IS KICKING UP A STORM IN STRUCTURAL BIOLOGY BY REVEALING THE HIDDEN MACHINERY OF THE CELL.”

X-ray Crystallography versus Single Particle Electron Microscopy

crystal
size eg $(100 \mu\text{m})^3$
unit cell eg $(100 \text{ \AA})^3$
Nr molecules 10^{12}

X-ray Crystallography versus Single Particle Electron Microscopy

Protein solution
Grid diameter 3 mm
Nr molecules $10^4 - 10^6$

In-silico crystallogenesi

“Resolution Revolution”

Science, 28 march 2015, Werner Kühlbrandt

*Advances in detector technology
and image processing
are yielding
high-resolution electron cryo-microscopy
structures of biomolecules.*

de novo model building

Bai, Fernández, McMullan & Scheres, Elife 2013
Fernández, Bai, Hussain, Kelley, Lorsch, Ramakrishnan & Scheres, Science 7 nov 2013

January 19, 2016

nature

In his **blog** late last week, NIH Director Francis S. Collins highlighted Cryo-EM Microscopy, the Method of the Year 2015.

Resolution

Courtesy: James Holton

Novel cryo-EM structures

ASC filament, *PNAS* Glycine receptor, *Nature* α -synuclein, *Nature* Stop codon, *Nature*

r-secretase, *Nature* K channel, *Nature* 60S, *NSMB* Piezo1 channel, *Nature* mP3R channel, *Nature*

Ljungan virus, *Nat* RNA pol, *Nature* spliceosome, *Science* inflammasome, *Science* 60S, *JSB*

2D projection of a 3D object

Phase contrast imaging with ideal detector

200kV, Cs=2.7mm, Cc=2.7mm, alpha=35mrad, DeltaE=0.7eV, amplContrast=10%,
pixelsize=1.86Ang

Introducing a Phase Plate (200kV)

200kV, Cs=2.7mm, Cc=2.7mm, alpha=35mrad, DeltaE=0.7eV, amplContrast=10%,
pixelsize=1.86Ang
-1 micron defocus

Volta Phase Plate

Danev et al, PNAS | November 4, 2014 | vol. 111 | no. 44 | 15635–15640

Visualising the conditioned spot @PP

Scale bar 5 microns

Danev et al, PNAS | November 4, 2014 | vol. 111 | no. 44 | 15635–15640

Phase Plate with varying phase shift

200kV, Cs=2.7mm, Cc=2.7mm, alpha=35mrad, DeltaE=0.7eV, amplContrast=10%,
pixelsize=1.86Ang
-1 micron defocus

Different conditioning schemes

Phase shifts determined inhouse

Worm Hemoglobin @200kV

pixelsize=1.25Ang, -1.5 micron defocus

Worm Hemoglobin @200kV with Phase Plate

pixelsize=1.25Ang, circa -1 micron defocus

90% of the human genome code
for proteins <100kDa

Tiesen et al, BMC Research Notes (2012) 5:85

Bovine Serum Albumin @200kV with Phase Plate

pixelsize=1.25Ang, circa -1 micron defocus

Introducing a Phase Plate, close to Scherzer

200kV, Cs=2.7mm, Cc=2.7mm, alpha=35mrad, DeltaE=0.7eV, amplContrast=10%,
pixelsize=1.86Ang
50 nanom defocus

Cryo-EM single particle analysis with the Volta phase plate

Radostin Danev, Wolfgang Baumeister, Elife march 7 2016

Cryo-EM single particle analysis with the Volta phase plate **in-focus**

Radostin Danev, Wolfgang Baumeister, Elife march 7 2016

Phase Plate with varying phase shift

200kV, Cs=2.7mm, Cc=2.7mm, alpha=35mrad, DeltaE=0.7eV, amplContrast=10%,
pixelsize=1.86Ang
-1 micron defocus

Using the Volta phase plate **with defocus** for cryo-EM single particle analysis

Radostin Danev, Wolfgang Baumeister, Elife 2017

Using the Volta phase plate with defocus for cryo-EM single particle analysis

Radostin Danev, Wolfgang Baumeister, Elife 2017

Imaging small proteins with the VPP

Khoshouei et al, Nature Communications, 30 June 2017
 Volta Phase Plate, Hemoglobin (64 kDa) at 3.2 Å.

Sample preparation: major bottlenecks

Inefficient sample application: >99,9% is blotted away.

Long exposure to air–water interface: can compromise quality of fragile macromolecular complexes.

Operator dependency: plunge vitrification interferes with automated sample handling.

The added thermal mass of the carriers that are required for automated handling prevents sufficiently rapid cooling of the sample.

Vitrojet™

VitroJet™: Blotless Sample Application

Pin-printing: TEM atlases overnight screening Autoloader content

Test sample:
 $c = 5\text{mg/ml}$
 $L = 1.5\text{mm}$
 $V = 0.5\text{ mm/s}$

Pin printing: Artica (200kV, Falcon3)

β -galactosidase 3.2Å

GroEL 3.7Å

Apoferritin 4.1Å

Worm hemoglobin 3.5Å

Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Institute

Thank you!

Questions?

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Q-SORT
A New Era
in
Electron
Microscopy

www.qsort.eu

Macromolecules within their native environment

The Cryo Tomography Workflow: Enabling *In Situ* Structural Biology

Courtesy: Alex Rigort, Thermo Fischer/FEI

Sample Preparation

Vitrified cells on grid

FEI Autogrids

Cryo-LM

Visualizing the molecular sociology at the HeLa cell nuclear periphery

Science

Julia Mahamid,^{1*} Stefan Pfeffer,¹ Miroslava Schaffer,¹ Elizabeth Villa,^{1,2}
Radostin Danev,¹ Luis Kuhn Cuellar,¹ Friedrich Förster,¹ Anthony A. Hyman,³
Jürgen M. Plitzko,¹ Wolfgang Baumeister^{1*}

“The lamella exhibits transparent amorphous ice at the edges of the cell.

However, the center of the cell clearly *undergoes incomplete vitrification* due to the low heat transfer capacity of biological material.

We thus avoided data acquisition deep inside the nuclear volume and choose to target areas at the front of the lamella for cryo-ET data collection.”

VitroJet for cells

Cryo-LM / Cryo FIB-SEM

M4I: greatly improved Cells on grid preparation

Maastricht University

Cryo TEM-lamella milling preparation

Courtesy: Alex Rigort, Thermo Fischer/FEI

M4I *In Situ* Structural Biology Workflow

VitroJet

Maastricht University

Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Insitute

Thank you!

Questions?

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Q-SORT

A New Era
in
Electron
Microscopy

www.qsort.eu

ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL